

REQUEST STRATEGIES IN CLASSROOM INTERACTIONS: A CASE STUDY OF ALGERIAN ARABIC-SPEAKING ENS-SÉTIF STUDENTS

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to investigate how Algerian Arab students (AAS, henceforth) use the speech act of requesting inside the classroom, while addressing their teachers. Requests are regarded as face-threatening acts, which is why request initiators are invited to be careful while using them in order to avoid communication breakdown and social antagonism, especially in situations where power, distance and language formality are observed, like in student-teacher communication inside the classroom. In this regard, this study unveils the request patterns favored by AAS to request something from their teachers and tries to explain the exigencies of these patterns. To this end, a discourse completion task (DCT) questionnaire was distributed to second year math students at the Ecole Normale Supérieure of Sétif, Algeria (a teacher-training higher education institution). The Questionnaire is made of four different classroom scenarios where students are likely to perform requests. Data were then coded and analyzed using Blum Kulka et al.'s (1989) Cross Cultural Speech Act Realization Project (CCSARP) famous coding conventions. AAS requests were analyzed from three different angles: level of directness, request perspective, and request modification. In relation to the level of directness, our findings have shown that AAS are inclined to using direct and conventionally indirect request strategies with an almost similar frequency, observing the dominance of the query preparatory head act. As far as request perspective is concerned, AAS are more favoured the speaker perspective. Finally, as for request modification, the participants tended to employ different modifications strategies, namely the 'من فضلك', equivalent of "please" in English.

Keywords: Algerian Arabic requests; Discourse completion task; request modification; Cross-Cultural Speech Act Realization Project; request perspective; classroom talk.

STRATÉGIES DE REQUÊTE DANS LES INTERACTIONS EN CLASSE : UNE ETUDE DE CAS D'ÉTUDIANTS ENS-SÉTIF ALGERIENS ARABOPHONES

Résumé : Le but de cette étude est d'examiner comment les étudiants arabes algériens utilisent l'acte de parole de la demande en classe, tout en s'adressant à leurs enseignants. Les demandes sont considérées comme des actes menaçant la face, c'est pourquoi les initiateurs de demandes sont invités à être prudents lorsqu'ils les utilisent afin d'éviter une rupture de communication et un antagonisme social, en particulier dans des situations où le pouvoir, la distance et la formalité linguistique sont observés, comme dans la communication étudiant-enseignant au sein de la classe. À cet égard, cette étude dévoile les modèles de demandes privilégiés par les EEA pour demander quelque chose à leurs enseignants, et tente d'expliquer les exigences de ces modèles. À cette fin, un questionnaire de tâche d'achèvement du discours (DCT) a été distribué à des étudiants de deuxième année de mathématiques à l'École Normale Supérieure de Sétif, en Algérie (un établissement d'enseignement supérieur de formation des enseignants). Le questionnaire est composé de quatre scénarios de classe différents où les étudiants sont susceptibles de formuler des demandes. Les données ont ensuite été codées et analysées en utilisant les conventions de codage célèbres du projet de réalisation d'actes de parole interculturels (CCSARP) de Blum Kulka et al. (1989). Les demandes des EEA ont été analysées sous trois angles différents : le niveau de directness, la perspective de la demande et la modification de la demande. En ce qui concerne le niveau de directness, nos résultats ont montré que les EEA sont enclins à utiliser des stratégies de demande directes et conventionnellement indirectes avec une fréquence presque similaire, observant la dominance de l'acte préparatoire

en tête de requête. En ce qui concerne la perspective de la demande, les EEA sont plus favorisés par la perspective de l'orateur. Enfin, en ce qui concerne la modification de la demande, les participants ont eu tendance à employer différentes stratégies de modification, notamment le « من فضلك », équivalent de « s'il vous plaît » en anglais.

Mots-clés : demandes en arabe algérien, tâche d'achèvement du discours, modification de la demande, projet de réalisation d'actes de parole interculturels, perspective de la demande, conversation en classe.

Introduction

Politeness is a central and universal phenomenon that is observed and appreciated at any given society. Studying it can give insights into a society's social values and relationships. At any community, people are likely to show, to a certain degree, how polite they are, how to show respect and deference, how to display face-saving, and attend to good manners either verbally or otherwise. In Arabo-Muslim communities, politeness and good manners in general are highly observed. This is what the Prophet Muhammed (peace be upon him) has insisted on since his first preaching journey, as he said "I was sent to uphold and complement ethical values", emphasizing another *hadith*/saying that "religion is good manners" and that "the (true) Muslim is the one from his tongue and hand Muslims are safe". The word tongue in the *hadith* refers to language and words. The latter have always had a strong presence in the Arab-Islamic culture. Because politeness is a pivotal quality in any society, it is informally acquired from family and society, and pupils are formally instructed about it at schools. Sayings like "be polite", "do not say this to your grandma" or "behave!" accompanied us since our childhood. Even people coming from uneducated backgrounds insist on teaching their children how to be polite because they know politeness is of great importance in communities, as it shows how much parents invested in bringing up polite respectful offsprings. Moreover, schools and educational institutions incorporate the teaching of politeness according to their culture and social norms. For example, while teaching English as a foreign language, politeness is often discussed in classroom subjects like linguistics and pragmatics. In this sense, Bella, Sifianou and Tzanne (2015:23) quote that "unlike native speakers who may be socialized into politeness in their native language, learners of foreign languages will have to learn how to behave politely." Politeness can be a major cause in the success or failure of many social interactions and relationships. For example, among the most noticeable speech events, where politeness is usually addressed and observed is while performing requests. The latter are said to be face-threatening acts (Brown & Levinson, 1987) because they imply some imposition from the speaker upon the hearer. For this reason, being (im)polite while performing requests is vital in many communicative interactions.

Although there exists plethora of studies on requests strategies and many other pragmatic topics (politeness, speech acts of various types) with reference to Arabic or Arabic-speaking learners (e.g., Alghazo, Zemmour, Al Salem, & Alrashdan, 2021; Atamna, 2016; Dendenne, 2014) yet most of these studies focused on the EFL context, with lesser attention given to the native-native interactions, in particular the use of requests by Arab native speakers using Arabic. Similarly, the same could be said about the Algerian context. To the best of the author's knowledge, there are no previous research that has studied the use of polite requests by Algerian Arabic speakers in a higher education context. Therefore, this paper aims to investigate this area, where politeness is likely to be greatly

observed. Furthermore, this paper aims to analyze and demonstrate the different patterns used by AAS while performing requests and attend to being respectful and avoid breaching politeness norms/maxims in this context. To achieve this, this research tries to answer the following questions: What level of directness AAS use while addressing requests to their teachers inside the classroom? What request modifications AAS employ in their requests? And why? What type of request perspective (speaker, hearer or impersonal) AAS are inclined to utilize while performing requests? Therefore, it is hypothesized that AAS are more direct, use hearer perspective and employ various modifications to their requests.

1. The Speech Act of Requesting

According to Trosberg (1995:187), requests can be defined as “an attempt of the requester/speaker to get the requestee/the hearer to do something for his benefit”. Similarly, Blum-Kulka et al. (1989) define requests as “the speaker’s expectation towards some perspective actions on the part of the hearer.” Because requests entail a degree of imposition by the speaker, they are classified as face-threatening acts (Brown & Levinson, 1987, p. 65); in other words, “requests may harm the social self-image of the requester and the recipient.” Basically, a request constitutes of two main elements which are the Head Act (HA) and Supportive Moves (SMs). According to Blum-Kulka et al. (1989), The HA is the minimum unit by which a request is realized while the supporting moves have two main functions: mitigators or intensifiers of the force of the request.

e.g. “*I forgot my money at home, could you lend me some money, please?*”

According to Blum Kulka et al. (1989), in terms of directness levels, a request can be classified into three main categories, which are: direct, conventionally indirect, and non-conventionally indirect. These three main categories are further subdivided into nine mutually exclusive categories. The direct strategies include mood derivable, performatives, hedge performative, obligation statements, and want statements; the conventionally indirect strategies include suggestory formulae and query preparatory; and non-conventionally indirect include strong hints and mild hints. Table 1 below summarizes these categories with examples.

Table 1

The main request head acts (Blum-Kulka, House, & Kasper, 1989, p.18)

Descriptive Category	Examples
Mood derivable	Clean up the kitchen / Move your car
Performative	I am asking you to move your car
Hedged performative	I would like to ask you to move your car
Obligation statement	You will have to move your car
Want statement	I would like you to move your car
Suggestory formulae	How about cleaning up/ Why don't you come and clean up the mess you made last night?
Query preparatory	Could you clean up the mess in the kitchen?
Strong hint	You have left the kitchen in a right mess
Mild hint	We don't want any crowding (as a request to move the car)

Blum Kulka (1987:131) based on her study on polite request in Hebrew and English, that “The most indirect request strategies were not judged as the most polite ones” . Hence, indirectness does not necessarily imply politeness in all languages/cultures.

2. Studies on the Speech Act of Request

According to Yazdanfar and Bonyad (2016), studies of requests strategies is divided into three categories which are cross-cultural, interlanguage, and single-language. Therefore, this section will be devoted to discussing previous research on Arabic requests across these three categories.

2.1 Cross-cultural Approach

Blum Kulka’s et al. (1989) Cross Cultural Speech Act Realization Project CCSARP is a pioneering approach that thoroughly investigated how certain speech acts (requests and apologies) are realized in different lingua-cultures. The aim of this project was to highlight similarities and differences that exist between languages in terms of realizing requests and apologies to showcase the universal features that may exist among the languages under investigation. In the Arabic context, numerous studies have been conducted to compare the use of various speech acts in the different Arabic dialects to a number of English varieties (e.g., British, American, and Australian English). For instance, Nelson et al. (2002) compared directness and indirectness in Egyptian and American style of communication; Mohamed (2019) and Alaoui (2011) compared Moroccan Arabic to American English in terms of request, offers, and thanks; AlMujaibel and Gomaa (2022) compared request strategies in Kwaiti Arabic and British English; Abuarrah et al. (2013) compared request strategies in Palestinian Arabic and British English; Tawalbeh and Al-Oqaily (2012) investigated politeness and requests in Saudi Arabic and American English; these are just a few studies to cite.

2.2 Interlanguage Pragmatic Approach

This type focuses on second language learners, mainly EFL and ESL learners, and how their pragmatic knowledge in interaction is developed. Moreover, this research strand takes into consideration the role of instruction in raising EFL and ESL students’ pragmatics awareness and competency, studying how these learners may or may not match native speakers in terms of their pragmatic competency. For instance, Abed’s (2011) study of pragmatic transfer of Iraqi EFL students; Dendenne’s (2017) analysis of the realization of requests and apologies among Algerian students and their American/British counterparts; Alqarawi’s (2018) comparison of the use of requests and apologies between Saudi EFL learners and American native speakers; Lenchuk and Ahmed’s (2019) study of directness in performing requests among Omani EFL learners and American native speakers; Bataineh and Bataineh’s (2008) study on apologies are some examples to cite. As a case in point, Dendenne (2017) conducted a cross-cultural study investigating the realization of requests and apologies in Arabic and English. Using Natural Semantic Metalanguage and Cultural Scripts as frameworks for data analysis and the DCT as the tool for data collection of two speech acts requests and apologies among AAS and their Anglo-American counterparts. Concerning the part of the study that deals with requests, the researcher found that conspicuous differences can be noticed between the two samples. While Anglo-Americans tend to frequently employ indirect requests/ interrogative directives, Algerians were more inclined to use bare imperatives even with someone who is ‘above’ in the social status, such

as university professors. Nonetheless, Algerian Arabic native speakers tend to soften the directive nature of their requests using some lexical items after pronouncing the request head act, as the researcher explained.

2.3 Single Language Method

This type focusses on studying how requests are realized in a given language without comparing it to any other language. Although there are some recent attempts to study some languages from a single point of view, studies in this type remain scanty. In the context of Arabic, we can find of such recently published studies in relation to some Arabic dialects: Saudi Arabic Moussa (2022); Jordanian Arabic (Almasaeed, 2023), Al-Adaileh (2023), and Rababah (2023); Emarati Arabic (Deveci & Hmida (2017)). However, as far as Algerian Arabic is concerned, to the best of my knowledge, I could not find a non-comparative study conducted in an academic setting worth citation in this regard. Therefore, my study on the use of requests strategies by Algerian Arabic native speakers in the classroom context aims to fill this research gap. It attempts to demonstrate how Arab Algerian students use request's patterns and show politeness in terms of request head act, request perspective and request modification.

3. Methodology

This section deals with the methodology for data collection and analysis. It describes the tool used for data collection, the participants involved in the study, the methods for analyzing the data, and the rationale behind decisions taken in every step. The popular Discourse Completion Test (DCT) is the method I opted for to collect data for this study after I surveyed different data collection techniques. According to Varghese and Billmeyer (1996:2), the DCT is a "questionnaire containing a set of very briefly described situations designed to illicit a particular speech act". This technique has been adopted by Blum-Kulka et al (1989) in CCSARP, dealing with requests and apologies in eight different languages. After that, the technique has become a very popular instrument in eliciting data for pragmatics research. The DCT has gained a wide popularity among researchers thanks to its reliability, ease of use, and its potential to collect huge amount of data in a short period of time (Varghese and Billmeyer, 1996; Manasrah & Al-Delaimi, 2008). However, although the DCT is a widespread effective data collection tool, it has some limitations and drawbacks. The main critic for this method highlights its inability to capture meaningful messages addressed through prosodic features and non-verbal language in oral interactions (Varghese & Billmeyer 1996; Chang, 2006).

Henceforth, a questionnaire consisting of six different discourse scenarios was employed to elicit responses from the sample of the study. In order to elicit a natural-like data, I emphasized to the participants that there is no right or wrong answer. The informants of this study are undergraduate Math students from the Department of Sciences at the Ecole Normale Supérieure of Sétif, Algeria. They were 50 students (48 females and 2 males), whose age ranged from 19 to 20. The students were a homogenous speech community whose native language is Algerian Arabic. The discourse situations were written in Arabic and students were informed to answer in any variety they might use in their interaction with their teachers. The four suggested situations include four open-ended questions. The six situations are summarized in both Arabic and English as follows:

لم تستطع فهم عنصر من الدرس وأردت من أستاذك أن يعيد الشرح، ماهي الصيغة التي تستعملها لتطلب منه ذلك؟

S1: If you cannot understand an element of the lesson, and you wanted your teacher to repeat for clarification, how would you request this?

تلقيت اتصالا مهما من أحدهم، و أردت أن تغادر قاعة الدرس، ماهي الصيغة التي تستعملها لطلب ذلك من أستاذك؟

S2: You have received an important call from someone, and you wanted to leave the room to answer it, how would you ask for the permission from your teacher?

أردت تغيير مكان جلوسك في القسم دون أحداث فوضي، ماهي الصيغة التي تستعملها لطلب ذلك؟

S3: If you want to change your seat inside the classroom without making noise, how would you ask this from your teacher?

تحصلت علي منحة للدراسة في الخارج و أردت من أستاذك ان يكتب لك رسالة تحفيز، كيف تطلب منه ذلك؟

S4: You gained a scholarship to study abroad and you want from your teacher to write for you a 'letter of motivation;' how would you request this from your teacher?

4. Data Analysis

As Table 3 indicates that out of 190 attempts of request made by students, 75 were direct, 74 were indirect, while non-conventionally indirect strategies were not observed at all. There are two subcategories of direct strategies which are mood derivable and want statements. As far as conventionally indirect strategies are concerned, query preparatory was the only subcategory observed, while suggestory formulae are absent from the corpus. Others include 16 elliptical phrases and 25 explanations. I will first analyze and explain the use of directness, then explain the use of elliptical phrases and explanations. It is discernible that both direct and indirect strategies are used almost with equal frequency, while the most striking fact is the total absence of conventionally indirect strategies. Moreover, the table indicates that the query preparatory is the most used core request strategy, followed by mood derivable and want statements in a sequence

Table 3:

Strategies	Direct strategy		Conventionally Indirect		Non-conventionally Indirect	other	
	Mood derivable	Want statement	Query preparatory	Suggestory formula		Elliptical phrases	Explanation
S1	22	00	9	00	0	12	5
S2	18	04	15	00	00	01	09
S3	12	7	21	00	00	01	07
S4	7	5	29	00	00	2	4
Total	59	16	74	00	00	16	25

Level of Directness Relative to the Requests Produced by AAS

4.1 Direct strategies

According to Blum Kulka et al. (1989, p11), directness is the “degree to which the speaker’s illocutionary intent is clearly expressed in the locution” which means that a speaker uses bare imperative to request something from the hearer. For example, a teacher asking a student to close the door he or she might say “close the door”. Therefore, direct requests are usually directed from the powerful/equal speaker to the less powerful/ equal hearer. However, direct strategies can also be used from the less powerful requester to the

powerful requestee as can be seen from Table 2. It is an agreed upon fact that teachers have more power over their students and the situation in the Algerian classroom is no exception. While performing requests inside the classroom, AAS used two main sub-direct strategies, which are mood derivable and want statement, yet with different frequencies. Out of 75 direct requests, there were 59 mood derivables and 16 want statements. Data shows less variability in relation to the choice of request strategies

4.1.1 Mood derivable

Mood derivables were dominant in S1 and S2, appearing 22 times and 18 times respectively. In S1, the request is about students asking their teacher to re-explain an element in the lesson because they did not understand it. The following are representative students responses using mood derivable:

Please! teacher, repeat for me this element.	من فضلك أستاذ، أعد لي شرح ذلك العنصر	1
Teacher, repeat for me this element, please!	أستاذ عاودلي العنصر هذا من فضلك	2
Teacher, repeat for me. I did not understand.	أستاذ، عاودلي ما فهمتش	3
Teacher, please, I did not understand this element, repeat it.	أستاذ، من فضلك لم أفهم هذا العنصر، أعد	4

In S2 students are asked to answer a question about the form they use to request leaving the room for a moment in order to reply to an urgent call. Student tend to use mood derivable and want statements more frequently to perform requests for this scenario. However, as indicated in Table 3, mood derivable is the most frequent direct strategy used by Algerian Arab students. The following are representative examples:

Teacher, I leave?	أستاذ، نخرج	5
Teacher, I leave for a minute, please?	أستاذ، نخرج دقيقة من فضلك	6
Teacher, do you allow me to leave?	أستاذ، أسمح لي بالخروج؟	7
Teacher, please I leave?	أستاذ، من فضلك نخرج	8

The use of the imperatives is considered by many request researchers (e.g., Blumkulka, 1989; Brown & Levinson, 1987) as a sign of impoliteness because they entail a superiority and the power of imposition from the speaker over the hearer. Therefore, students must avoid using imperatives with their teachers so as not to sound impolite. However, the use of mood derivable by AAS inside the classroom could have numerous justifications. First of all, the use of mood derivable is justified by the familiarity between the interlocutors. Being taught by the same teacher(s) for several months or years, students gradually get familiar with their teacher(s) as a result of their daily interactions. Hence, the social distance between them turns into closeness. The latter is clearly expressed through the use of mood derivable while performing requests. Second, AAS utilization of imperatives could be justified by emergency of compliance. In math classes such as the case of this study where every small detail is very important, interrupting the teacher's explanation with long sentences can be annoying for both students and teachers. Therefore, many students prefer

to be direct while requesting their teacher to re-explain a point in the lesson. That is to say, the situation does not permit for pragmatic norms/politeness scale negotiation by between teachers and students. Finally, from a linguistic point of view, Arabic has no specific linguistic formula to express politeness through request words/formulae. Therefore, the use of imperative is likely to be acceptable provided that there is something in the tone of the requestee that reduces imposition or the request is accompanied with some mitigating devices such as routine markers like “please”, “if you allow” and so on, as illustrated by examples 1, 2, and 4.

Want Statements Want statement is also used but with a low frequency. They appear in S2, S3, and S4 only.

The following are some examples that show the use of this strategy by AAS from S2 (Examples 9-11) and S4 (Examples 12-14).

Teacher, I want to leave for an important matter.	أستاذ، أود الخروج لأمر ضروري	9
Teacher, I want to leave, please.	أستاذ، أريد الخروج من فضلك	10
Teacher, I want to leave for a minute, please.	أستاذ، حاب نخرج دقيقة يعيشك	11
Teacher, please, can I take from your time and talk to you? I have got a scholarship to study abroad, and I want you to write for me a letter of motivation.	أستاذ من فضلك، هل يمكنني الأخذ من وقتك و التحدث معكم؟ حصلت علي منحة في الخارج و أتمنى ان تكتب لي رسالة تحفيز	12
I want you to write me a letter of motivation	أرجو منك كتابة رسالة تحفيز لي	13
Teacher, I want from you a letter of motivation.	أستاذ، أريد منك رسالة تحفيز	14

The first noticeable aspect about want statements as expressed by AAS is that they are realized through various ways. They include in addition to ‘want’ expressions as in Example 10 and 14, *wishes* as in example 12, *desires* as in Examples 9 and 11, and *plea* such as in Example 13.

4.2 Conventionally Indirect strategies

According to the coding scheme suggested by Blum-Kulka et al. 1989 (Table 1), Conventionally indirect strategies include suggestory formula and query preparatory. However, in the present study, and as it is shown in Table 2, only query preparatory strategies are observed. Suggestory formula are totally absent. The most striking finding in this section is the observation that query preparatory is the most used request formula by AAS. Utilized with varying frequency, query preparatory request strategies are present across the four suggested scenarios with a higher frequency in S4. The following groups of examples are from S1, S2, S3, and S4 respectively

Teacher please, I didn't understand that point, could you explain it to me?	أستاذ، من فضلك لم أفهم ذلك العنصر، ممكن تعيد شرحه لي؟	15
Teacher, please can you repeat this point? I couldn't not understand it.	أستاذ، من فضلك هل يمكنك اعادة هذه النقطة؟ لم أفهمها.	16
Teacher, please, could we repeat this element?	أستاذ، من فضلك، نستطيع اعادة ذلك العنصر؟	17

Although AAS tend to be more direct while asking for clarification during a lesson, some of them tend to use preparatory conditions as shown in the examples above. In S2 and S3, where students perform requests to ask for permission (e.g., to change their place, to leave the room), query preparatory has been used 15 times compared to 18 times for mood derivable and four times for want statements. The following are some examples illustrating the use of query preparatory in these two situations:

Teacher, can I leave for a moment?	أستاذ، أيمكنني الخروج قليلا	18
Teacher, can I leave for a minute?	أستاذ، ممكن نخرج دقيقة؟	19
Teacher, can I leave?	أستاذ، هل أستطيع الخروج؟	20
If you allow, can I change my place?	لو سمحت، ممكن أغير مكاني	21
Teacher, can I change my place?	استاذ، أستطيع تغيير مكاني؟	22
Teacher, can I change my place, if there is no problem?	أستاذ، هل يمكنني تغيير مكاني، اذا لم يكن (في هذا) مشكل؟	23

Query preparatory request strategy is the most dominant strategy in S4. It has been used by students 29 times compared to 11 times for other sub-direct strategies (4 times want statements and seven times mood derivable). For this situation, students were asked on how they would perform requests to ask their teacher to write them a letter of motivation after they have gained a scholarship to study abroad. The following are examples from S4, depicting the use of query preparatories in this situation:

Teacher, long life to you/Please, could you write for me a letter of motivation?	أستاذ، تعيش، اذا تقدر تكتبلي رسالة تحفيزية؟	24
Teacher, could you write for me a letter of motivation that would help in my studies?	أستاذ، تقدر تكتب لي رسالة تحفيزية تساعدني في الدراسة؟	25
Teacher, since you are my role model, could you write for me a letter of motivation?	أستاذ، باعتبارك قدوة لي، هل يمكن أن تكتب لي رسالة تحفيز؟	26
Teacher, thanks to the Almighty and thanks to you, I have gained a scholarship to study abroad, but I am hesitant, could you write for me a letter of motivation?	أستاذ، بفضل الله أولاً، و بفضلكم، تحصلت علي منحة لإكمال الدراسة في الخارج، و لكنني مترددة، هل يمكنك ان تكتب لي رسالة تحفيزية؟	27

Compared to the first three situations (S1, S2, and S3), S4 where query preparatory is strikingly dominant, is likely to take place outside the classroom or at the end of lessons. It is not part of the usual classroom interactions between students and their teachers. Moreover, asking a teacher for help in writing a letter of motivation is not like asking him or her for re-explanation. The latter is basically part of his duty while the former is not. We have seen in the previous section that AAS prefer direct strategies (mood derivables and want statements) while performing requests in routinescenarios, where familiarity takes over power and social distance. However, when the situation is very likely to occur outside the classroom, and is not part of the teacher's duty, it seems that students attend to the factor of power and social distance. Therefore, they tend to use conventionally indirect strategies embodied in the frequent use of the query preparatory request strategies.

4.3 Elliptical Phrases

Elliptical phrases are those phrases that do not include a head act and used in the context of request. They were used 16 times across the four situations. Their predominant

use appears in S1 (12 times). In the other situations, they were rarely used (Once/twice in every situation). The following are some typical examples:

Teacher, I could not understand!	أستاذ، لم أفهم
Teacher, please, I could not understand this element.	أستاذ، من فضلك لم أفهم ذلك العنصر
Teacher, I could not understand that part	أستاذ، ما فهمت ذلك الجزء
Teacher, may Allah grant you a long life/please, I did not understand how did we arrive to this element?	أستاذ يعيشك، ما فهمت العنصر هذا منين جا؟
Teacher please...	أستاذ من فضلك
If you allow...	لو سمحت

4.4 Explanations

Although students' responses to the DCT situations as Explanation do not clearly indicate the level of directness in their requests, I decided to include them in the analysis because they entail important aspects that would demonstrate how students perceive performing requests addressed to their teachers. For examples, some students indicate that they use gestures and body language when asking something from their teachers. Others indicate the importance of deploying intonation while performing requests. These two aspects cannot be captured by a written DCT questionnaire.

I raise my hand then I point to leave [usually pointing to the door] without talking.	أرفع اليد، ثم الإشارة بالخروج دون التحدث
If the teacher was explaining, I raise my hand and I point that I want to change my place [by pointing to another seat] without talking, making noise so as not to interrupt him.	إذا كان الأستاذ يشرح، نرفع يدي ونشير بلي رايحة نغير المكان دون التكلم او التشويش و مانقاطعوش.
I rias my finger [the index] so that the teacher can see me, then I change my place.	أرفع اصبعي حتي يراني الأستاذ ثم أغير مكاني.
I ask for permission with a lower voice.	الاستئذان بصوت منخفض.

In the case of using body language, students mention the use of raising their hands or pointing to something (place they want to sit in or the door to leave). For instance, in S2 and S2 as is shown in the examples above, raising hands to ask for permission inside the classroom is considered in the Algerian and many other cultures as a sign of politeness and respect towards teachers. Moreover, some students refer to modulate their voice tone while asking for permission to do something inside the classroom. They choose to speak in sotto voce to ask for permission as is shown in the examples above. Speaking with a lower voice is also regarded as a sign of politeness and a way of showing respect towards the addressee.

4.6 Request perspective

Table 4

Request Perspective as Used by AAS

Situation \ Perspective	Speaker	Hearer	Joint	Impersonal
S1	11	31	00	00
S2	35	05	00	00
S3	23	02	00	00
S4	07	24	00	00
Total	75	66	00	00

Table 4 shows the patterns of request perspective used by AAS in this study.

The first noticeable finding in table above is that only speaker-oriented and hearer-oriented request perspective are used in this study. Joint and impersonal perspectives were not observed at all. In total, speaker-oriented requests (75 times) have been used more than hearer-oriented ones (66 times). However, the two patterns have different frequency across the study's four scenarios. Hearer-oriented have been dominant in S1 (with direct strategies) and S4 (with conventionally indirect strategies), while speaker-oriented have been dominant in S2 (with direct strategies) and S3 (with conventionally indirect strategies). In general, there is a balance in the use of hearer and speaker-oriented patterns. Not involving embarrassment and control over the hearer, speaker-oriented request are considered more polite strategies (Blum Kulka & Olshtain, 1984). Following this argument, AAS tend to employ speaker orientation in their requests in order to reduce imposition and not threatening the face of their teachers. In fact, speaker-oriented perspective sound like asking for permission. This is the case in S2 and S3 where students employ the speaker perspective to ask for permission to change their place or to leave the classroom. This is shown in Examples 5, 6, and 8 in S2 with direct strategies and in Examples 18, 19, and 20 in S3 with conventionally indirect strategies. As far as the hearer-oriented perspective is concerned, Brown and Levinson (1987) suggest that the use of this perspective can be considered more embarrassing and hence threatening to the hearer's face. Thus, hearer-oriented can be considered impolite form of making requests and they are better be avoided. However, in the Algerian Arabic context, as Dendenne (2017, p. 10) argues, hearer-oriented requests are not perceived as a "threat to one's personal autonomy". Thus, they are accepted in the Algerian culture in general. Hearer-oriented requests have been dominant in S1 with direct requests such as in Examples 1, 2, 3, and 4, and in S4 with query preparatory, such as in Examples 24, 25, 26, and 27. Grammatically speaking, these request strategies/formulae require necessarily the hearer-oriented perspective.

4.7 Request Modification

Given that request in the examined classroom situation tend to be very considerate and non-interrupting, it comes as no surprise that fewer request modifiers have been used. AAS have used various types of request modifications to achieve different purposes. Their use ranges from lexical and syntactic downgraders, terms of address, hedging, prayers, apologies, and so on.

The most used external modifier by AAS is *من فضلك*/*min fadhlik*, equivalent of *please* to the extent that in many cases AAS make their request elliptically, just by saying it without a head act. This is shown in examples 1, 2, 4, 6, 12, 15, 16, and 17, to mention but a few. Moreover, this modifier appears with every type of request. It is used with mood derivable, want statement, elliptical phrases and query preparatory. We believe that the use of *min fadhlik* is identical to *please* in English requests, which, as Borovina (2017) seconds, its use with directives aims to reduce imposition on the hearer and thus protect their face. While its use with indirect requests (in our case query preparatory) as an emotional sympathizer is meant to show how badly someone is in need to do to ask for the favor; and also as a request illocutionary force indicating device (Faerch & Kasper, 1986), especially when it stands by itself or used with elliptical requests.

Another important request modification which is probably specific to Arab and Islamic cultures is the use of prayers and religious formulaic expressions. Among the religious expressions that are encountered in our data is “May Allah grant you long life” = “ربي يعيشك او تعيش” or “May Allah protect you” = “ربي يحفظك” Praising and thanking the Almighty to show respect and good deeds such as saying “Thanks to Allah and to you” = “بفضل الله ثم بفضلكم”, This type of modification has been used widely in S4 where students ask their teacher to help them write a letter of motivation. AAS tend to apply this specific type of modification for different intentions. Using religious expression tend to reiterate the interactants shared religious beliefs Islam appreciates helping others and being in one’s needs. Therefore, accepting the request, in whatever form is performed, is not because of the speaker’s imposition, rather it is perceived as accepting the Almighty’s commands and fulfilling them. Moreover, AAS use some types of internal modifications such as interrogative sentences, if clauses and modals. Interrogatives have been used widely by AASs. Interrogatives in Arabic can be realized through different forms including using interrogative particles such as “هل” “is /are/can” or the question particle الهمزة . Question word “هل” is shown in Examples 26, 27, and 16 above.

If clause in Arabic is realized through the particle “لو” , “if you allow” = “لو سمحت” or اذا = “if”. Instances of this kind are shown in Examples 7 , 21, and 23.

Interrogatives, just like “if clauses” in English, are used with both direct and indirect strategies and they are used by students to check if it is possible to ask or do something in the class. They are used to minimize imposition and protect the teacher’s face. This leads me to highlight an important fact about requests in Arabic. In fact, Arabic does not contain many specific grammatical forms for making requests, unlike say English and many other Indo-European languages. Requests in Arabic are basically expressed through imperatives irrespective of the addressee’s social power or the distance between interlocutors. However, power relation is only recognized when the mitigating devices are supplied, like when asking the Almighty, and requests become prayers that have a specific linguistic structure that distinguish them from other types of requests, and, thus, assign to them a higher politeness value. Muslims usually say “Allah’umma” to ask or pray to Allah for something, in religious formal settings like in mosques and wedding rituals.

5. Discussion

Data analysis has shown that AAS use direct and conventionally indirect strategies while neglecting the use of non-conventionally indirect strategies. This means that AAS avoid the use of non-conventionally indirect strategies when interacting with their teachers, paving

the way to an equal use of direct and conventionally indirect strategies. This goes in line with Almasaeed (2023) who found that the non-conventionally indirect strategies were completely avoided by Jordanian Bedouin Arabic students when interacting with people of higher power. Moreover, when using direct strategies, AAS limit their choice to certain subcategories, namely mood derivable and want statement, while they solely opt for the query preparatory from the many conventionally indirect strategies. This finding is in accordance with Farag (2022) study on the use of request in study and work by Saudi Arabic speakers. She mentioned that the limited choice of core request strategies is basically connected to the intrinsic structural nature of Arabic, a language which has little options compared to say English and other European languages, especially for the head acts. Concerning the want statements, they seem to us that they are more softened than their counterpart in English. Want statements are used by AAS to ask for permission. The latter has no imposition and therefore protect the face of the hearer. The analysis of the four classroom scenarios involving AAS demonstrated that the query preparatory is the most used core request strategy. It is deemed appropriate for the situation where power relations are observed. Students inside the classroom are certainly less powerful and therefore their request towards their teachers should be articulated with no imposition and must protect their face and their teachers'. Therefore, the indirectness of the query preparatory helps AAS to observe politeness by minimizing imposition, as Alaoui (2011, p. 9) puts it "the more indirect the speaker makes his/her request the more polite s/he is". This finding is in accordance with Mohamed's (2019) study who reported that query preparatory was the most dominant strategy among Moroccan Arabic speakers when performing requests. On the other hand, this contradicts with Dendenne (2017) who found that bare imperatives were the predominant core request strategies among Algerian students while interacting with someone 'above' in status, such as a university professor. This contrast in findings suggests that more large-scale studies on requests is still needed in the Algerian context. As far as request perspective is concerned, data analysis shows that AAS largely prefer the speaker-oriented perspective. The latter avoids the reference to the addressee as the doer of the action and, hence, can minimize the request imposition, which in turn make the request more polite (Blum-Kulka & Olshtain, 1984; Brown and Levinson, 1987). Therefore, the predominance of speaker-oriented among AAS is meant to stress students' role, making their requests sound more asking-for-permission than genuine requests. Therefore, we can safely say that most of students' requests in the classroom are in fact structurally phrased as asking for permissions. However, this finding again disagrees Dendenne's (2017) on Algerian EFL students and with Mohammed's (2018) on request perspectives in Yemeni Arabic; both researchers found that hearer-oriented is the predominant request perspective in both Algerian Arabic speakers' performance (even when using a foreign language) and Yemeni Arabic ones. Both researchers claim that this trend is culturally accepted from the standpoint of Arabic. For instance, Mohammed (2018) claims that the Yemeni are less bothered to use the hearer-oriented perspective because this is what is the expected norm, imposed by both society and Arabic grammar. Moving to request modification, AAS use various types of internal and external modifications. The use of the equivalent of the English internal modification "please" or "من فضلك" in Arabic is predominant in the students' requests to the extent that sometimes some students would make a request just by a self-standing "please" or "من فضلك". Therefore, the use of this internal modification has in fact a double function. It may work as a mitigator that reduces the request imposition especially when it is placed with direct or indirect request head acts. Second, it works as a replacement of the head act itself

when it is used in elliptical phrases, and, thus, marks a request illocutionary force. An Algerian student may just say “please” to request something from his or her teacher. Moreover, AAS sometimes resort to their religious background to modify their requests. Because religion plays an important role in the Algerian society, AAS seem to understand the strong illocutionary force of religious expressions. Adjusting one’s request with prayers and religious sayings may remind the hearer that requesting him or her is done out of modesty rather than imposition. In this respect, I think that further large-scale studies on request modification in the Algerian context would clearly reveal their importance and power in making and changing requests. Following my intuition as a native speaker of Algerian Arabic, I believe that what matters most in making requests is not the directness in the head act; it is rather how we use mitigating devices or modification. In this respect, it is suggested that “mitigation can index politeness regardless of levels of directness used by speakers” (Blum Kulka, 2005, p. 266). However, such a claim has to be supported with more evidence from future studies on request modifications and how they are received by Algerian Arabic speakers.

Conclusion

This study has investigated the structures and use of the speech act of request in Algerian Arabic in an academic setting. In terms of request head acts, it has been noted that Algerian Arab students deploy a limited number of request head acts comparing to the wide range of options suggested by Blum Kulka et al (1989). The only three request strategies used were the query preparatory, the mood derivable and want statements with the query preparatory as the predominant used head act. If the use of the query preparatory fits with power position and the social distance between students as requesters and teachers as requestees, the use of mood derivable and want statement might look questionable for non-native Arabs. However, the analysis has revealed that the use of these two direct strategies is linked to language economy in daily-routine classroom interactions as in the case of mood derivable, and to the fact that want statements in Arabic sounds more as asking for permissions with no inherent imposition on the addressee. In this respect, researchers are warned to carefully investigate the illocutionary force of the direct request in Arabic and how they are perceived by listeners. The study has also found that AAS largely employ the speaker-oriented request perspective. The latter allows them to minimize imposition and make their requests sound more as asking-for-permission. Moreover, the study has noted the use of different request modifications with “من فضلك” (equivalent of “please”) as the predominant modification along with the incorporation of some religious sayings and prayers specific to the Algerian Arabo-Muslim culture. Although this study can partly help us understand and identify how AAS use the speech act of request in an academic setting, I urge researchers to further investigate the use of this speech act in large-scales, and in different social, cultural, and educational backgrounds. Although I am fully aware that the findings of this study may not be generalized to the wider Algerian academic context, it is worth noting that they can have several implications in different contexts. First, this study sheds light on the importance of single language studies in the speech act of request especially in the Algerian context, well beyond ethnocentric-based comparative studies conducted with reference to dominant language like various varieties of English. Identifying and understanding the request patterns used by AAS while interacting with their teachers from their L1 perspective and according to their cultural norms will eliminate conflicts inside and outside educational settings, especially for non-native speakers of Arabic or even those

Arabs who are strongly influenced by their L2 linguistic and cultural norms. For instance, as an English teacher for over a decade, I (and probably many other colleagues) would find it so rude if a student requests me directly (with a bare imperative of the mood derivable type). In some cases, I would not reply to such type of requests at all. Moreover, understanding how native speakers of Algerian Arabic perform requests in their mother tongue, would help researchers in intercultural pragmatics identify and explain areas where linguistic transfers are likely to occur among Algerian foreign language learners when performing requests (e.g., in English, French).

References

- Abed, A. Q. (2011). Pragmatic transfer in Iraqi EFL learners' refusals. *International journal of English linguistics*, 1(2), 166. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijel.v1n2p166>
- Abuarrah, S., Lochman, K., & Lutjerhams, M. (2013). Cross cultural pragmatics requests' use of strategy and level of directness in Palestinian Arabic and British English. *An-Najah University Journal for Research-B (Humanities)*, 27(5), 1109-1144.
- Al-Adaileh, Bilal A. "Off-record indirectness in Jordanian Arabic" *Journal of Politeness Research*, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1515/pr-2022-0047>
- Alaoui, S. M. (2011). Politeness principle: A comparative study of English and Moroccan Arabic requests, offers and thanks. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 20(1), 7-15.
- Alghazo, S., Zemmour, S., Al Salem, M. N., & Alrashdan, I. (2021). A cross-cultural analysis of the speech act of congratulating in Kabyle and Jordanian Arabic. *Ampersand*, 8, 100075. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amper.2021.100075>
- Ali Al-Natour, M. M., Maros, M., & Ismail, K. (2015). Core request strategies among Jordanian students in an academic setting. *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)*, 6(1), 251-266. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2834446>
- Al-Marrani, Y. M. A., & Sazalie, A. (2010). Polite request strategies by male speakers of Yemeni Arabic in male-male interaction and male-female interaction. *The International Journal of Language Society and Culture*, 30(30), 63-80.
- Almasaeed, N. R. O. (2023). Effects of social power and distance on the realization of requests in Jordanian Bedouin Arabic. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 10(5), 29-44. doi.org/10.29333/ejecs/1728
- AlMujailbel, Y. B., & Gomaa, Y. A. (2022). Request strategies in Kuwaiti Arabic and British English: A cross-cultural pragmatic study. *Randwick International of Education and Linguistics Science Journal*, 3(1), 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.47175/rielsj.v3i1.401>
- Alqarawi, N. (2018). Learner-centered comparison study between American native speakers and Saudi English language learners in forming English requests and refusals in academic settings (Doctoral dissertation, Colorado State University).
- Atamna, E. (2016). Requests politeness strategies in Algerian learners of English academic emails. *Journal of Human Sciences*, 05-29.
- Aubed, M. M. (2012). Polite Requests in English and Arabic: A Comparative Study. *Theory & Practice in Language Studies*, 2(5). <http://doi.org/10.4304/tpls.2.5.916-922>
- Bataineh, R. F., & Bataineh, R. F. (2008). A cross-cultural comparison of apologies by native speakers of American English and Jordanian Arabic. *Journal of pragmatics*, 40(4), 792-821. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pragma.2008.01.003>
- Bella, S., Sifianou, M., & Tzanne, A. (2015). Teaching politeness. *Teaching and learning (im) politeness*, 23-51. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781501501654>

- Blum-Kulka, S. (1987). Indirectness and politeness in requests: Same or different?. *Journal of pragmatics*, 11(2), 131-146. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-2166\(87\)90192-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-2166(87)90192-5)
- Blum-Kulka, S., & Olshtain, E. (1984). Requests and apologies: A cross-cultural study of speech act realization patterns (CCSARP). *Applied linguistics*, 5(3), 196-213.
- Borovina, D. Š. (2017). Croatian EFL learners' interlanguage requests: A focus on request modification. *ELOPE: English Language Overseas Perspectives and Enquiries*, 14(1), 75-93. <https://doi.org/10.4312/elope.14.1.75-93>
- Brown 1980. How and why are women more polite: some evidence from a Mayan community. In McConnell-Ginet, Borker and Furman, eds.
- Brown, P., & Levinson, S. (1987). *Politeness: Some universals in language usage*. Cambridge University Press.
- Chang, Y. F. (2006). An Inquiry into Pragmatic Data Collection Methods. Online Submission.
- Dendenne, B. (2014). 'Could you help me with these bags brother?: My shoulders are falling.' Transfer in interlanguage requests performed by Algerian EFL learners. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 10(2), 29-47.
- Dendenne, B. (2017). A cross-cultural study of speech act realisations in Arabic and English: A cultural-scripts approach. *Revue Académique des Études Sociales et Humaines*, 18,(3), 3-15.
- Deveci, T., & Hmida, I. B. (2017). The request speech act in emails by Arab university students in the UAE. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 13(1), 194-214.
- Faerch, C. (1989). Internal and External Modification in Interlanguage Request Realization. *Cross-Cultural Pragmatics: Requests and Apologies*.
- Ide, S., Hill, B., Carnes, Y. M., Ogino, T., & Kawasaki, A. (2012). 11. The concept of politeness: An empirical study of American English and Japanese. *Politeness in Language*. 281-298. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110199819.281>
- Lakoff, R. T. (1989). The limits of politeness: Therapeutic and courtroom discourse.
- Leech, G. 1983. *Principles of pragmatics*. Longman.
- Lenchuk, I., & Ahmed, A. (2019). Are the speech acts of EFL learners really direct? The case of requests in the Omani EFL context. *SAGE Open*, 9(1), <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244018825018>
- Manasrah, M., & Al-Delaimi, Z. (2008). Politeness in request strategies used by native speakers of Jordanian Arabic at Irbid National University. *Indian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 34(1-2), 169-187
- Mekboul, M. (2020). A sociolinguistic study of Forms of politeness among the Algerian Speakers: The case of Ibn Khaldoun University Students (Tialet) (Doctoral dissertation).
- Mohamed, H. (2019). Request strategies and level of request directness in Moroccan Arabic and American English. *IOSR Journal of Humanities And Social Science*, 24(8), 10-20. <https://doi.org/10.9790/0837-2408081020>
- Moussa Farrag, N. (2022). Saudi politeness: Request and apology in the Context of study and work at King Abdulaziz University: A pragmatic study. *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)* Volume,13, 300 -312. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4085844>
- Nelson, G. L., Al Batal, M., & El Bakary, W. (2002). Directness vs. indirectness: Egyptian Arabic and US English communication style. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 26(1), 39-57. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0147-1767\(01\)00037-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0147-1767(01)00037-2)

- Rababah, L. (2023). Examining speech acts in Jordanian advertising: Pragmatic functions, linguistic features, and rhetorical devices. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 10(5), 212–223. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejecs/1722>
- Shoshana, B. K., House, J., & Kasper, G. (1989). Cross-cultural pragmatics: Requests and apologies. *Grazer Linguistische Studien*.
- Tawalbeh, A., & Al-Oqaily, E. (2012). In-directness and politeness in American English and Saudi Arabic requests: A cross-cultural comparison. *Asian Social Science*, 8(10), 85. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v8n10p85>
- Trosborg, A. (1995). Requests, complaints and apologies. *Mouton de Gruyter*.
- Varghese, M., & Billmyer, K. (1996). Investigating the structure of discourse completion tests. *Working Papers in Educational Linguistics*, 12(1), 39-58.
- Yazdanfar, S., & Bonyadi, A. (2016). Request strategies in everyday interactions of Persian and English speakers. *Sage Open*, 6(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244016679473>